

CATERA ZEBUART: FROM THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE BUDDHIST ENTREPRENEURSHIP STUDENT CREATIVITY PROGRAM

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Abstract

Buddhist Business and Management is the first study program in Indonesia that integrates business, management and Buddhist studies. It is important that scientific integration is carried out in this study program so that it can contribute to the treasures of thought in the business and management science cluster. This study offers a conceptualization of a Buddhist-based entrepreneurship program. The method used in this study is a project-based participatory qualitative. Methods in participatory studies have a strong commitment to developing social, economic, and cultural aspects. As well as the studies used in the discussion of this article corroborate these aspects. The subjects of this study were three students of the Buddhist Business and Management study program and a supervisor. Through business development analysis, product selection in the form of painting and calligraphy based on Zen Buddhism art, combined with the wisdom philosophy of the archipelago in the form of letters and deep meanings, and the use of eggshell waste as a product characteristic that is part of the astronomic. This product is given the name Catera Zebuart, an abbreviation of Eggshell Nusantara Zen Buddhism Art with the number EC00202234669 Registration Letter from the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, Republic of Indonesia. Submission of proposals on this artwork was able to enter the Student Creativity Development competition funded by the Sub-Directorate of Higher Education, Directorate General of Buddhist Community Guidance, and Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia.

Keywords: Utilization of Eggshell Waste, Artwork, Zen Buddhism, Archipelago Wisdom, Creative Economy, Buddhist Entrepreneurship.

A. INTRODUCTION

The economic downturn during the COVID-19 pandemic is not only felt in Indonesia. Most countries in the world are experiencing the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in the economy. According to the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy/Tourism and Creative Economy Agency (Kemenparekraf), Republic of Indonesia (Administrator, 2021c), that 2021 has been designated as the International Year of Creative Economy for Sustainable Development in the session to -74 General Assembly of the United Nations (UN) Resolution Number A/RES/74/198 Year 2019 (Danjon, 1960). The Government of the Republic of Indonesia is the initiator of this resolution and is supported by 81 sponsoring countries. The International Year of the Creative Economy for Sustainable Development 2021 is the right momentum to encourage global recovery during the pandemic. The creative economy's significant contribution of 3% to Global GDP continues to have the potential to grow, making it a formidable economic sector strengthened by a surge in digitalization and services.

According to the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, this resolution is one of the efforts to refocus the creative economy sector as an important contributor to the global economy. The creative industry has shown resilient growth in international trade, including trade in creative goods and services, as well as its contribution to the global economy. The creative economy also has the potential to contribute to the achievement of the 2030 sustainable goals, by promoting economic growth and innovation, reducing poverty, creating jobs and decent work for all, improving the quality of life and empowering women and youth, and reducing inequality both within and between countries. . In particular, for example, 2021 is the Momentum for the Recovery of the Creative Economy of West Java Province (Administrator, 2021). And the Banten Province Tourism Office (Administrator, 2021) which will hold continuous coaching for creative economy business actors in 2021. Thus, this study explains how Lecturers as academics work with Buddhist Business and Management students, Sriwijaya State Buddhist College, which is located in Tangerang Regency, Banten Province, Indonesia, is able to conduct a conceptual study of the integration of Buddhist-based business and management science and implement it practically through the creative economy for global economic recovery efforts!

The creative economy is one of the supporting bones of a country's economy. Today, from observations related to the creative industry, it seems that it is increasingly actively developing. Thus, through it is expected to be able to absorb the increasingly higher workforce and it is certain that unemployment will decrease. Economic development in Indonesia has progressed from an economy that only relies on the natural sector, towards products that are the result of creation. Plus the support from marketplaces that empower the community to increase the value of the products produced. So that these products are able to be competitive in the international arena, namely by having export quality standards. Indonesia's economic trend is growing with the themes of creativity and innovation. Through this study, students jointly see business opportunities by creating products that answer the problems that exist in modern society, which are full of pressure and cause depression.

The field of art is one of the fields included in the creative economy. Painting, for example, supports tourism businesses. Through artistic entrepreneurship, this study seeks to answer the challenge of providing enlightenment to modern society by using painting and calligraphy based on wisdom-based Zen Buddhism extracted from characters, words, and meanings from the archipelago (present-day Indonesia) as well as the use of eggshell waste to add product value. The combination of a modern Zen lifestyle with the use of household waste can make a work of artistic value as well as economic value. Academic education has the challenge of putting conceptual studies into contextual practice. Students together with their supervisors for Buddhist business and management study programs are challenged to develop a business that combines business management knowledge and Buddhist religion. Selection of products that combine elements of Zen, archipelago wisdom, and the use of eggshell waste to be able to participate in student creativity programs in the field of entrepreneurship and obtain financial support from the government. However, how are students and their supervisors able to contribute to applying business and management scientific studies that are integrated with Buddhist religious principles into the entrepreneurship program in the products they create!

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. CATERA ZEBUART ARTWORK

Catera Zebuart is an abbreviation of Eggshell Archipelago Zen Buddhism Art with the Registration Letter number EC00202234669 from the Ministry of Law and Human Rights, Republic of Indonesia. Catera Zebuart is interpreted as a conscious art work based on Zen Buddhism that raises the themes of the wisdom of the ancient archipelago and today's Indonesia. Where Indonesia has cultural diversity. This mindful art product combines painting, calligraphy, and framing of mashed eggshell waste as a supporter of the philosophy of repeated birth and death in Buddhism. Like works of art with the theme of zen buddhism, each has its own characteristics (see also, Arts, 2011; H Kara, 2014; Levine, 2016; Cookson and Stirk, 2017; Lomas et al., 2017; Masuda and O'Donohue, 2017; Lim, 2019; Lee and University, 2021). However, the elements of simplicity, enlightenment and mind breaking are inherent in Zen art.

According to (Lomas et al., 2017), concerns that the largely secular way of 'de-contextualization' in which mindfulness tends to be taught and practiced in the West undermines its potential for relief from psychosomatic symptoms and enhancing spiritual life. Thus, there is an emerging attempt to 're-contextualize' mindfulness, which refers to the broader framework of Buddhist ideas and practices within which it was originally developed. They focused on the early concepts of Zen Buddhism, and in particular on the principles of Zen aesthetics. It focuses on seven principles identified by Hisamatsu (1971) in his classic text *Zen and the Fine Arts*: kanso (simplicity); fukinsei (asymmetry); koko (loud majesty); shizen (naturalness); daisuzoku (freedom from routine); sei-jaku (tranquility); and yu-en (great grace).

The presence of these principles in zen-based artwork reflects and communicates insights that lie at the heart of Buddhism, such as simplicity, serenity and non-attachment. Moreover, on top of their application to the creation and appreciation of art, aesthetic principles have the capacity to promote health-related well-being, and to encourage a more real and authentic understanding or concern. Mindfulness, as taught by the Buddha nearly 2600 years ago, most likely influenced the style and format of Zen aesthetics when they became established after the twelfth century. They hope that today's Zen aesthetic principles can be used to influence and enhance one's understanding of mindfulness, amid concerns that its 'spiritual essence' is being lost. Of course, there is a need for empirical investigation of the potential of aesthetic principles to inform the design of mindfulness-based care approaches as well as to facilitate authentic conscious living. Based on these aesthetic principles, Catera Zebuart was also developed.

However, Catera Zebuart's work is not only developed based on authentic and aesthetic principles in Zen. This work of art also adds elements of words, meanings and cultural diversity of the archipelago (present-day Indonesia) which have enlightening wisdom values. For example, the word "welum" means life which comes from the Dayak language, Kalimantan Island, Indonesia. Elaboration of eggshell waste has been widely carried out in scientific studies in the field of chemistry and its use in various fields of life (as shown in

A.M. King'ori, 2011; Hempe, 2020; Article, 2021; Baláž et al., 2021). In other fields, eggshell waste is also used in sculpture. According to (Senior et al., 2019) sculpture is one of the subjects studied in cycle II and universities in Ghana. Due to its relevance to the socio-economic development of the country, the materials for the production of sculptures became of great importance. In some Second Cycle institutions where Fine Arts study, much of the material for the production of sculptures is imported, expensive or inaccessible to students due to insufficient funds to purchase materials for studio work. This has limited Fine Arts teachers and students with limited materials resulting in less and monotonous practical work, making students lose their effective mastery, skills in sculpture production.

Eggshells from hatcheries, homes and the fast food industry have been used for art for centuries around the world. But they have also been disposed of as waste materials which can cause environmental pollution in several places including Indonesia. This participatory research uses egg shells as part of a storynomic built on Catera Zebuart's art products. Eggshell powder for production forms the periphery of Catera Zebuart's paintings and calligraphy and has a philosophical meaning about birth and death, and the conditions of suffering that many beings experience in the world (Pāli: "sorrow," "suffering") , Sanskrit Duhkha, in Buddhist thought, the true nature of all existence. Therefore, this product targets people's interest, especially Buddhists and modern people who need wisdom and peace from the practice of life as it is that Zen Buddhism has to offer to the world.

2. Business Development

Business owners who start trying to market products must master product and product marketing. Both startups, small and medium enterprises, and even large companies must be able to master market conditions. (Astuti and Murwatiningsih, 2016) stated that (1) management ability has a partial effect on business performance. (2) Business characteristics have a partial effect on business performance. (3) Management ability and business characteristics have a simultaneous effect on business performance. Therefore, business owners must pay attention to market conditions so that the products they produce can be known by the public. Support from the local government in charge of the business sector is needed to market any products.

Specifically in the field of painting, it was revealed (Yuliani and Zakiah, 2021) that painting from the Jelekong Art and Culture Village has spread to foreign countries using the 7P marketing mix which includes (Product, Place, Price, Promotion, People, Physical Evidence, and Process) by the artist community in Jelekong. Based on the results of their study, obtained information about the marketing of paintings in Jelekong Art and Culture Village by carrying out promotions which include personal selling, public relations, direct marketing, events sales promotion. From all forms of promotion mix, the main priority for promotion is public relations, direct marketing, and events.

As explained earlier, in this study the products developed were paintings and calligraphy based on Zen Buddhism art, combined with the wisdom philosophy of the archipelago in the form of letters and deep meanings, and the utilization of eggshell waste as a characteristic of

the product that became part of the storynomic and was given a trade name. Catera Zebuart. The place for the development of this artwork is in the Swirijaya States Buddhist College campus, which is located in the Bumi Serpong Damai area, South Tangerang City. This area is a strategic place for the development of creative art products based on Zen Buddhism where this place is an independent city area that is growing rapidly and not far from the capital city of Indonesia, Jakarta. Even though there are challenges for products or entrepreneurs of similar painting and calligraphy works, lecturers and students of the Buddhist Business and Management Study Program can make this an opportunity for business cooperation. It even gives students the opportunity to explore their skills, of course with a typical storynomic in this entrepreneurship through Cati Zebuart's painting and calligraphy works.

Furthermore, the marketing of this product is supported by a joint policy with the Government of the Republic of Indonesia; Ministry of Religion, Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, and Ministry of State-Owned Enterprises in 2021, to realize Mendut Temple, Borobudur Temple and other temples as places of worship for Hindu-Buddhist people, as well as world tourist destinations. Similar to tourist objects in Asia based on world places of worship such as stupas (Dai, 2021); Buddhist Temple Sites and Relics (Liu, Jiang and Cao, 2021); the Sacred Site Mount Putuo (Pan and Yan, 2021); Longchang Monastery of Mount Baohua (Zhou, 2022); Stacked Stone Pagodas (Zhao, 2021); Likewise, the reliefs at Borobudur Temple (Kandahjaya, 2015) and other temples (Sensitivity, 2016) have interesting stories as tourist destinations based on places of worship. So that it has the potential to be used as a strategic direct marketing place for Catera Zebuart's artwork.

3. Conceptualization of Minimum Investment Policy (IMK)

Product selection and observing business opportunities are very important. However (Kaukab, 2021) shows that when taken into account as an independent variable, only the ability to exploit new business opportunities has a significant effect on brand expansion equity, while entrepreneurial orientation and introduction of business opportunities do not. This shows that exploiting capabilities is the most important in increasing brand extension equity. Previous studies have identified that exploitation is better than exploration in a simple context, which has an optimal approach. This shows that the brand extension problem is seen as the best solution. Therefore, there needs to be exploitation to provide superior performance for the company. For this reason, it is necessary to develop the power of brand extension for Catera Zebuart products. So as to be able to attract people in the art market and solve problems that is the goals of a social business. Thus, setting a minimum selling price and the strength of product imagery in the community for lovers of Zen painting and calligraphy, as well as outside the community with the aim of enlightening, is very necessary.

Conceptualization of the Minimum Wisdom Investment (IMK) price, intersects the concept of social entrepreneurship, the Buddhist economic concept which is represented through the concept of white ocean strategy in the context of global marketing. The study (Wulan and Hermanto, 2019), assumes that sociopreneurship plays an important role in facing the challenges of world economic development. This is because sociopreneurship is something

unique because it combines a social mission and a business discipline. Of course, over the past few years, sociopreneurship has proven to be a very effective strategy to solve social and environmental problems, create job opportunities for marginalized groups, ensure sustainable development, and reduce poverty. Sociopreneurship creates fundamental changes to approach development challenges, enabling people to initiate and take responsibility rather than (only) demanding change (Suyatna and Nurhasanah, 2017; Surniandari et al., 2019; Wulan and Hermanto, 2019). Furthermore, according to (Kusumasari, 2015; Suyatna and Nurhasanah, 2017; Alremeithi and Kudus, 2021; Istianingsih and Defit, 2021; Mazeed, 2022; Muhammadiyah et al., 2022; SMK, 2022) social, economic and environmental challenges in the world now is an opportunity for a sociopreneurship or entrepreneurship mindset to initiate change and produce a positive impact on society. Apart from that, the Minimum Investment in Wisdom is determined through understanding and implementing the view of economic behavior in Buddhism which is represented by the strategy concept of creating a white ocean (White Ocean Strategy). However, according to (Chanchaochai, 2013) white ocean strategy is not a static achievement, but a dynamic process that must be carried out continuously. The basic principle of a white ocean strategy in a company and its business must be based on honesty, sincerity, morality and ethics. No less important is setting long-term goals by paying attention to the balance between human factors, nature, profit and individual social responsibility. From the threat in building the Catera Zebuart business, which is related to the emergence of similar entrepreneurs, the management of this business turns that threat into strength through cooperation. Cooperation is carried out by optimizing campus functions in exploring the potential of other students in making similar works. However, it remains within the framework of the astronomic peculiarities that were built in the making of Catera Zebuart. Here 50% of the profits go to the artist who created the work. In addition to the profits used to empower and optimize the potential of students on campus where this program is carried out, 8% of the profit from the sale of Catera Zebuart's painting and calligraphy works is divided into the Paramitha Fund program in collaboration with the Directorate General of Buddhist Community Guidance - Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia and the Directorate General Taxes—Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia. Like the Amil Zakat Agency contained in the Islamic concept, this Paramitha fundraising Foundation or donation must legally be approved by the two directorates. One example of a foundation that has a legal basis is the Indonesian Buddhist Paramitha Fund Foundation. Then the formulation is obtained as follows:

$\text{Minimum Price for Goodness Investment} = \text{Total Production Cost} + \text{Total Unit Profit Margin}$
$\text{Cost Per Product} = \text{Total Production Cost} : \text{Total Production Unit}$

Where the Total Unit Profit Margin is distributed:

1. 8% for Paramitha Fund Foundation Program
2. 50% for Artists (assisted by Catera Zebuart management)
3. 42% for Management

42% Profit Margin received by the Management is used for administration, and returned to the community in the form of empowerment programs related to the development of Catera Zebuarart products. This empowerment program does not only provide basic product-making skills that will become an income for the artist. However, empowerment is given to build an enlightening positive mentality related to the value behind Catera Zebuarart's products that provide wisdom—enlighten society.

C. METHOD

This study uses a project-based participatory qualitative method. According to (Creswell, 2015) this approach must involve learning and learning activities as well as teaching practice. It was also conveyed (Ozanne and Saatcioglu, 2008; Morales, 2016; Kosasih, 2018; Muhtarom, 2019; Rahmat and Mirnawati, 2020; Rahman et al., 2021; Z, Sari and Prihati, 2021), general ideas and problems in the research. This must be under control, attract interest and ability, and something to be developed. In this participatory study method, has a strong commitment in developing social, economic, and cultural aspects. The subjects of this study were three students of the Buddhist Business and Management study program and a supervisor.

D. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Process of Creating a Catera Zebuarart Artwork

Catera Zebuarart's Painting and Calligraphy Artworks were made by (1) Conducting a zen-themed workshop on Buddhism and elaborating the wisdom-rich works of characters, words and meanings that are being explored in various parts of Indonesia today (formerly the archipelago); (2) Collecting eggshell waste around the campus environment and processing it into powdered granules; (3) Incorporating eggshell powder into the outer frame of the painting paper and forming a single storynomic product; (4) Mounting a pre-made Catera Zebuarart design. (5) The last process is input into the frame or frames that have been provided. The storynomic of each product is different according to the meaning that will be conveyed, except for the eggshell powder which is made separately and pasted in the product catalog. This information can be read if the product is displayed on social media or marketplaces. The following is an example of Catera Zebuarart's Artwork along with the storynomic.

Welum (from the Dayak language): “A life-giving energy. Like a tree, through its leaves it absorbs carbon and returns oxygen energy to life.”

The following is a special meaning of Catera Zebuart products, namely eggshell powder that resembles sand that surrounds the image media. This powder is analogous to grains of sand with the following message: "Frames the many births and deaths, the many sufferings of creatures in the universe, like the amount of sand in the Ganges, I learned to be wise and enlightened" #caterazebuart by DG, ink on rice paper 130x60 cm

2. Business Development and Management Results

Businesses engaged in social entrepreneurship that emphasizes nobler goals, such as tackling problems that exist in society such as poverty (Surniandari et al., 2019). Meanwhile, Catera Zebuart's Artwork with the Motto: A Work of Mindfulness towards Enlightenment hopes to provide a positive mental awakening and heal art lovers from mental poisons. Social entrepreneurship can have a positive impact and provide solutions as a step to advance society and earn profits. Social entrepreneurship combined with the white ocean strategy approach does not only solve the economic problems of the community. However, its development is expected to be in the values of moral nobility. The white ocean strategy and social entrepreneurship model are business concepts that introduce morality, honesty, ethics, fairness and anti-corruption in the company's driving mechanism, thus enabling the company to gain the trust of the public, which in turn will continue to grow and advance in the future. This will come. So that the concept of social entrepreneurship is in line with the concept that we run especially among today's youth (see also Suyatna and Nurhasanah, 2017; Surniandari et al., 2019; Wulan and Hermanto, 2019).

This business opportunity is carried out according to a plan that has been prepared by the team through a proposal which is then submitted to the Student Creativity Program held by the Sub-directorate of Higher Education, Director General of Buddhist Community Guidance, and Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. This business experience gave a deep satisfaction to the team, especially the three students, through implementation observations and interviews related to the results of the implementation of this research, the three students thought that, "during this activity we are like caterpillars that transform into butterflies."

This entrepreneurial experience is described as a caterpillar transforming into a butterfly with the following aspects. (1) enjoy tranquility and mental awakening in producing works of art which are the development of creativity and innovation that combines elements of Zen Buddhism, Archipelago wisdom, and the utilization of eggshell waste which means helping the movement to save the earth; (2) attracting suitable and high-prestige stores in the direct sale of Catera Zebuart products; (3) promotion in marketing an interesting product. When put into practice for example by utilizing marketplaces and social media we learn many of these skills; (4) Can practice the concept of social entrepreneurship, white ocean strategy in the context of the Buddhist economy through the policy minimum investment formula.

Sociopreneurship according to a study (Suyatna and Nurhasanah, 2017) as a career trend for young people today is not wrong. Students involved in this program really enjoy the process

of digitizing marketing. Not only that, how the students penetrate the potential of the direct selling business that is aimed at being a source of pride. Catera Zebuart's products are able to work together with the Craft Shop and Spiritual Shop "Shambala Inner Shop" which is a special value for them. Products that are acceptable in this store have very high criteria and are also sold at high prices. This shop is also located in Gading Serpong, close to the campus area. Through this direct selling, the perception and motivation of students in this study increased. And stated that they would definitely be able to penetrate the direct sales market found in religious tourism supported by the government's program on Borobudur and Mendut Temple as religious tourism destinations and tourism in general. This even initiated them to continue their marketing efforts through the worldwide Zen Buddhist-based art community and global marketplaces such as Amazon.

Integration and application of secular and religious scholarship in Buddhist business and management study programs at Sriwijaya States Buddhist College is important (Sulaiman, 2020). The production of Catera Zebuart's artwork went smoothly and was acceptable to direct selling shops that apply high standards and local marketplaces. Catera Zebuart is a handicraft product that utilizes eggshell waste and combines it with elements of Zen Buddhist art. The development of products characterized by the archipelago, such as from several regions in Indonesia such as Lombok, Java, Kalimantan is still widely open. This product also processes waste into products of artistic and economic value. Catera Zebuart also underwent several design changes which were poured into the astronomic starting from the design, manufacturing method, and packaging. This continues to be evaluated using a product evaluation sheet. The products produced after getting inputs from consumers are used as materials to make improvements in subsequent production, to produce products that are worthy of being marketed among the wider community.

E. CONCLUSION

The realization of this research activity enhances the experience of students of the Buddhist Business and Management Study Program. Practicing concepts in class into the context of business development in the creative economy. This is in line with the Indonesian government's policy through the United Nations Letter on the World Creative Economy in 2021. Art product innovation that provides inner enlightenment for the community is very much needed in today's world full of stress and mental poison. Solving community problems is also in accordance with the sociopreneurship principle. It is hoped that this work of art can continue to develop and be marketed in order to support the government in the declaration of Borobudur Temple, Candi Mendut, and others as religious tourism and general tourist destinations. In network marketing, this product is expected to be able to penetrate the well-known marketplaces in the world.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization of Buddhist Concept of Business and Management and Analysis, S.G. and P.S.; Methodology, S.M. and R.I.; Data Collection, Review, and Analysis, S.

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